

**EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON PENDING ON DEMOGRAPHIC
DEVIDEND IN INDIA
(A META-ANALYSIS)**

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Paper Received On: 20 JAN 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 FEB 2025

Published On: 01 MAR 2025

Abstract

The year 2020 and 21 have been very bad for India and the world. When Corona started showing its wrath, human life came in danger. It has inflicted wounds on us at every level, the economies of many countries have collapsed. During this time unemployment and hunger were very high. But the Indian government resorted to lockdown to combat this disease. Due to the imposition of lockdown and sudden stop of traffic, the migrant labourers had to face the most. The effect of the lockdown was reversed on human life, where the lockdown and unemployment forced the poor people and migrant labourers to return their home villages. The worst condition of this disease was of migrant labourers, who walked in lakhs of hungry and bare feet towards their local village along with their wives and children. Women were also not untouched by the effect of Corona. According to a World Bank report, more than 12 million people in India have reached the condition of poverty. Sexual violence, online harassment and domestic abuse have increased during the Corona period. As of 10 August 2021, a survey conducted last year (between June and August 2020) showed that on return to their villages, there was an average decline of up to 85 percent in the income of migrant workers.

Due to unemployment, common men life has become more painful than before. It was found in many surveys that the effect of Covid-19 has been on people's employment and pockets. The survey found that a total of 66 percent of the people's pockets have been affected by Covid-19. 28 per cent of the people were cut in their wages, 25 per cent people worked without pay and 17 per cent people lost their jobs. The lockdown imposed by the Government of India and the government order not to go out of the house closed the whole of India. This had a direct impact on employment. Factories were closed. The employment of common man and migrant labourers was snatched away which forced them to return

to their homes. The CMIE report said that between January and March, the number of jobs in India fell from 411 million to 39.6 million and the number of unemployed increased from 320 million to 38 million. Therefore a decline of 90 lakh in the labours force results in a fall of 15 million in the number of workers and an increase in the number of unemployed by 60 lakh. But the way the Modi's government is dealing with the corona epidemic, 84 percent of the Indians who participated in the survey are satisfied with the policies of the central government. In comparison, only 43 per cent in the US, 56 per cent in the UK, 53 per cent in Hong Kong and 71 per cent in Australia were found to be satisfied with the government's work in dealing with the pandemic.

Key words: Covid-19, Examining, Impact, pandemic, demographic, dividend

Introduction:

The year 2020 and 2021 has been very bad for India and the world. It has given us wounds at every level, while moving towards this global recession, the wound of Corona (Covid-19) is so deep that the economy of many countries has collapsed. During this time unemployment and hunger were very high. But to combat this divine disease in India from the very beginning, the central government of India resorted to lockdown. The first lockdown was announced by the Prime Minister on 25 March 2020 and panicked by the ban on movement out of the house for 21 days, the workers left their places for the ancestral home. After that many times the migrant labourers had to face the most problems due to the imposition of lockdown and sudden stoppage of traffic. When there was a problem of food for the labourers, they left the house on foot and somehow reached their home after walking hundred kilometres.

The impact of the lockdown was reversed on human life where the lockdown and unemployment forced the poor people and migrant labourers to return to their villages. At the same time, the adamant and wordy attitude of the Central Government of India also got exposed. The worst condition of this disease was of migrant labourers, who walked in lakhs of hungry and bare feet towards their local village along with their wives and children. During the Covid-19 period, small children, sick old people, pregnant women were also walking on bare feet. Little children who did not even know the meaning of burden and luggage. But they were being carried without slippers. They all had a hope that somehow they reach back to their inherent home. Due to which they will be able to survive and get two times of bread. In this Covid-19 era, unemployment, exhaustion of deposits, non-receipt of salary, became a scourge in leprosy for the poor people of India.

Many times the central and states government appealed to the people to help the public of the poor section. Big industrialists and companies did not listen to the government, the situation at the ground level kept getting worse. Many times relief packages of crore was given to small

and big companies by central and states government. But at the bottom level it all turned out to be false. In this epidemic, the common man started feeling helpless. In the end they felt that if they have to die of hunger then they should go back near their village and family members for die because in this epidemic, their own country have become like a stranger for them.

What is a Corona Virus?

Corona viruses are a large family unit of viruses that cause illness ranging from the common cold to more severe diseases. Find out more about this novel corona virus that has not been previously recognized in humans. Most people infected with the virus will experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and get well without requiring special treatment. However, some will become seriously ill and require medical attention.

How was Covid-19 named?

Corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is a novel disease caused by a newly identified virus, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Corona virus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). The novel disease which begun in Wuhan (China) in Dec.2019. International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV) announced “severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)” as the name of the new virus on 11 February 2020. This name was chosen because the virus is genetically related to the corona virus responsible for the SARS outbreak of 2003. But WHO announced “COVID-19” as the name of this new disease on 11 February 2020, following guidelines previously developed with the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). That means Corona Virus Disease -19.

What are the symptoms of COVID-19?

Symptoms can include fever, cough and shortness of breath. In more severe cases, infection can cause pneumonia or breathing difficulties. More rarely, the disease can be fatal. These symptoms are similar to the flu (influenza) or the common cold, which are a lot more common than COVID-19. This is why testing is required to confirm if someone has COVID-19.

Need and Importance of the Study:

Every person was untouched by effect of covid-19. All human afraid by it. Women were also not untouched by the effect of Covid-19. According to a report of the World Bank, more than 12 million people have reached the condition of poverty in India. Its injury on both urban and rural women is increasing. According to a report of the National Commission for Women (NCW) 2020, cases of violence against women were found more during the Corona period than

normal period. Therefore, gender-based violence is increasing in India since the end of last year. In this, the epidemic has added fuel into the fire and there has been increased in sexual violence by online harassment and domestic abuse. The National Commission for Women (NCW) received 5,297 complaints of domestic violence in 2020, compared to 2,960 in 2019. During the last year nationwide lockdown, women became victims of domestic violence on a large scale. This trend also continues in this year. 2000 cases of crime against women have come before the National Commission for Women in 2021. About a quarter of these cases are of domestic violence. However, these figures do not tell the truth completely as many women facing violence prefer to remain silent rather than raise their voice against such crimes. Thus, It can be said that there has also been an increase in sexual violence during the Covid-19 period, whose effect is also being seen on our social relations.

When Covid-19 started showing its wrath, human life came in danger. Covid-19 had an impact on every aspect of human life. Its effect also put brakes on the speed of the never-stopping Indian Railways. The economies of many countries collapsed. It also shattered the thoughts of the country of India sitting with the dream of becoming a developed country. The lockdown imposed by the Government of India and the government order not to go out of the house, closed the whole India. This had a direct impact on employment. Factories and industries were closed. The employment of common man and migrant labourers was snatched away which forced them to return to their homes. Therefore, The researcher embodied the research work on this burning problem.

Objectives of the study: There are following objectives of the study.

1. To study the impact of covid-19 on women life.
2. To study the impact of covid-19 on employment.
3. To study the Government's role in containing the impact of covid-19.

Hypothesis of the study: There are following hypothesis of the study.

1. There was significant impact of Covid-19 on women life.
2. There was significant impact of Covid-19 on employment.
3. There was significant satisfaction the Government's role in containing the impact of Covid-19.

Research Method: Meta-analysis is a quantitative, formal, epidemiological study design used to systematically assess previous research studies to derive conclusions about that body of research.

Testing Hypothesis and Data analysis :

Objective 1. To study the impact of covid-19 on women life.

H₀₁- There was no significant impact of Covid-19 on women life.

Analysis: As the report of <https://www.orfonline.org/> on 10 August 2021, a survey conducted last year (between June and August 2020) showed that there was an average decline of up to 85 percent in the income of migrant workers on return to their villages. The deposit savings of such families kept declining. In many cases, families faced difficulties in repaying their existing loans. Not only this, they also had to spread their hands in front of others to meet their basic needs. The burden of debt increased on women to maintain the migrant members of the family returning from the cities to the villages. Therefore, women in rural areas have to face more challenges than in cities. Due to which their life have become more painful than before.

Thus null hypothesis was rejected and research hypotheses was accepted. Therefore, we can say that *'there was significant impact of Covid-19 on women life.'*

Objective: 2. To study the impact of covid-19 on employment.

H₀₂. There was significant impact of Covid-19 on employment.

Analysis: In December 2020, Praja Foundation Mumbai conducted a survey on 2087 families (www.ndtvnews.com/ Jan.30, 2021), showing the impact of the corona virus on people's employment. It was found in the survey that the effect of corona virus has been on the employment and pockets of the people. This is now becoming clear from many surveys. According to this survey, the employment of 66 percent people was affected by corona, out of which 17 percent people also became unemployed. The results revealed in the survey conducted by Praja Foundation Mumbai, it was clear that the employment of a large number of people was affected due to corona virus. Apart from this, unemployment also increased in the country. The survey found that a total of 66 percent of the people's pockets have been affected by corona. 28 per cent of the people were cut in their wages, 25 per cent people worked without pay and 17 per cent people lost their jobs.

Many families in villages depend on money sent home by permanent or seasonal migrants. In such a situation, there is a direct impact on the immigrants returning home and their families when income declines. "A survey conducted last year (between June and August 2020) showed that on return to their villages, there was an average decline of up to 85 percent in the income of migrant workers." (10 Aug., 2021, <https://www.orfonline.org/>).

As same a report of New Delhi, According to the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE), the unemployment rate in the country has increased to 7.97 percent during April 2021,
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from 6.5 percent in March. According to the research firm, this happened due to the lockdown imposed to reduce the speed of the corona virus. According to the research firm Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy, more than 7 million people lost their jobs in the country during April 2021. This increased the unemployment rate in the country to 7.97 percent, which was 6.5 percent in March. CMIE Managing Director Mahesh Vyas said that there has been a decline in jobs due to the stalled business activities due to the lockdown. (May03, 2021, <https://hindi.news18.com/>).

The CMIE report (2020) said that between January and March, the number of jobs in India fell from 411 million to 39.6 million and the number of unemployed increased from 320 million to 38 million. Therefore a decline of 90 lakh in the labour force results in a fall of 15 million in the number of workers and an increase in the number of unemployed by 60 lakh. (April 15, 2020, <https://hindi.oneindia.com/>).

Thus null hypothesis was rejected and research hypotheses was accepted. So, we can say that *'there was significant impact of Covid-19 on employment.'*

Objective: 3. To study the Government's role in containing the impact of covid-19.

H₀3. There was no significant satisfaction the Government's role in containing the impact of covid-19.

Analysis: Central government is dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic, 84 percent of the Indians surveyed are satisfied with the policies of the central government. In comparison, only 43 per cent in the US, 56 per cent in the UK, 53 per cent in Hong Kong and 71 per cent in Australia were found to be satisfied with the government's work in dealing with the pandemic. (May 06, 2020, <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/>)

Thus null hypothesis was rejected and research hypotheses was accepted. Therefore, we can say that *'there was significant satisfaction the Government's role in containing the impact of covid-19.'*

Findings of the Study:

There are following finding of the study.

1. There was significant impact of Covid-19 on women life.'
2. There was significant impact of Covid-19 on employment.'
3. There was significant satisfaction the Government's role in containing the impact of covid-19.

Implication of the Study:

The Covid-19 has brought the whole world to its knees. During the Corona period, the unemployment rate has also gone up several notches in India. India was already going through an economic slowdown, but now the employment rate in India has reached the lowest level so far in March. At this time the unemployment rate entered double digits for the first time. According to data from the Centre for Monitoring Economy (CMIE), the unemployment rate in India stood at 23.8 percent for the week ended March 29, up from 8.4 per cent a week ago. In the next week ending March 5, the unemployment rate increased further to 23.4 percent. Data show that unemployment in India has been increasing progressively since January after the first case of corona virus was reported in India. CMIE said the employment rate fell to its all-time low of 38.2 per cent in March and the scenario worsened as the country went into the lockdown period. India has reported double-digit unemployment rates in urban areas in the past, but this has never happened in rural India. As the effective nationwide lockdown has replaced it with a nationwide lockdown of 21 days. The CMIE report said that between January and March, the number of jobs in India fell from 411 million to 39.6 million and the number of unemployed increased from 320 million to 38 million. Therefore a decline of 90 lakh in the labour force results in a fall of 15 million in the number of workers and an increase in the number of unemployed by 60 lakh. (April 15, 2020, <https://hindi.oneindia.com/>).

The economy of the whole world has been hit hard due to the Corona crisis. There was a shortage of cash in the business-industry world. In such a situation, salary cuts, layoffs of people also started. According to a research report, during this period of Corona crisis, about 86 percent people were afraid of losing their jobs. This was revealed in a research report by the British research firm Crosby Texture Group. According to the survey, people lived in the shadow of fear of losing their jobs and livelihood due to the Kovid-19 pandemic. The highest 86 percent of Indians included in this survey were worried about losing their jobs. In comparison, only 31 per cent in the UK, only 33 per cent in Australia, 41 per cent in the US and 71 per cent in Hong Kong were worried about job loss.

But an important question is this when a student studying in a university in Wuhan had returned to India and the Indian government confirmed the first case of corona virus in Kerala on 30 January 2020, Why did the government not impose restrictions on citizens coming from abroad? When the number of positive cases of Covid-19 was up to 500 in India till March 22, 2020. So that Prime Minister Narendra Modi appealed on March 19 to all citizens to observe 'Janata-Curfew' on Sunday, March 22 from 7 am to 9 am. On 24 March, Narendra Modi had

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announced a nationwide First lockdown for a period of 21 days from midnight of that day and he had also said that the lockdown would be enforced stricter than the Janata-curfew, so how did the citizens enter in the country who were coming from abroad? Did the government do homework for him before imposing the lockdown? If the answer to all these is no, then the government should take responsibility for this unemployment. The saddest aspect of the Corona period was that the Covid-19 disease has come from abroad, has come by airplane, which has been brought by big rich people.

Whom the government took on its lap and its cost had to be paid by the very poor, daily wage workers living in the slums and still put all the blame on these poor, migrant, labourers and slum dwellers. In this work, the media also shamed humanity and said that these people are spreading the disease. What is the irony that we are doing politics on this too? The rich would get hospitals, but the poor started thinking that by staying here, they have to die anyway. Who will take care of us? Which doctor will see my wife and children without money? How many days will we live without eating? So risking his life, he left for his villages on foot. During this crisis, the Gurudwaras, showing humanity, opened their pandals and gates for these labourers and migrants. Other religions can also learn the passion shown by the Sikh community in helping and distributing food along the way. We got acquainted with ourselves in the crisis of Covid-19 period. At such times the government, media and we should have stood for humanity, but we failed to do so.

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